

Red hydrated. [Found: Co, 34.22; H₂O, 20.60. Co (CN)₃, 2H₂O requires Co, 34.10; H₂O, 20.81 per cent]. $\chi_m(t_{30}) = 21.79 \times 10^{-6}$; $p_{W_{\text{air}}} = 15.04$; $p_{W_{\text{air}}}$ corrected = 15.16.

Cobaltic alum was prepared according to the method described by Marshall (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891 59, 760) by electrolysis in a divided cell in the cold. The large blue crystals were removed, rapidly dried by means of filter paper and examined at once in a Curie's balance. [Found: Co, 11.98. Co₂(SO₄)₃.(NH₄)₂SO₄.24H₂O requires Co, 12.16 per cent]. $\chi_m(t_{31}) = 0.48 \times 10^{-6}$; $p_{W_{\text{air}}} = 13.76$; $p_{W_{\text{air}}}$ corrected = 14.29.

Cobaltic sulphate was prepared by electrolysis in the cold in a divided cell as described by Copeaux (*Compt. rend.*, 1905 140, 657). The blue crystals were dried and examined as before. $\chi_m(t_{30}) = 11.28 \times 10^{-6}$; $p_{W_{\text{air}}} = 15.71$; $p_{W_{\text{air}}}$ corrected = 16.05.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

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The Complex Formation between Manganese or Aluminium with Tartaric Acid in Alkaline Medium.

By S. P. GOVEL AND B. L. VAISHYA.

The present work is in continuation of the work carried out by Raman and Vaishya on complex formation between cerium or tungsten with tartaric acid in alkaline media (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 179).

EXPERIMENTAL.

In order to work with manganese chloride and potassium tartrate in alkaline solution and to ensure that no precipitate is formed under ordinary circumstances, it is found to be essential to add only sufficient quantity of alkali so that the whole of the manganese salt is transformed into hydroxide and there is only slight

excess of alkali. The solution thus prepared was found to have a colour which deepens on keeping. The solution, it was found, could be rendered colourless by exposure to the sun and would continue to be colourless if kept out of contact of air and not otherwise.

Table I gives the results obtained with the polarimeter. The optical rotation goes on decreasing and reaches a minimum when the solution contains 1 mol of potassium tartrate to 1 mol of manganese oxide. The effect of temperature is clear from Table II. Table III contains the results obtained by the *e.m.f.* method. The p_H was found to show a rapid change at the same place at which complex formation is observed.

Manganese Oxide and Potassium Tartrate.

TABLE I.

K-tartrate = 3.39 g./100 c.c.

MnO.	K-tart. : MnO.	α_D^{15}	$[\alpha]_D^{15}$
0.0000 g./100 c.c.	1 : 0.0	1.9°	28.02°
0.2173	1 : 0.166	1.4	19.40
0.4346	1 : 0.333	1.2	15.70
0.6519	1 : 0.500	1.1	13.60
0.8692	1 : 0.666	1.0	11.70
1.0865	1 : 0.833	0.9	10.04
1.3038	1 : 1.000	0.7	7.40
1.5211	1 : 1.166	0.7	7.10

TABLE II.

Temp.	...	15°	25°	31°
α_D	...	0.7°	1.0°	1.2°
$[\alpha]_D$	...	7.4°	10.6°	12.7°

TABLE III.

Molar prop. of K-tart : MnO	...	1 : 0	1 : 166	1 : 333	1 : 5	1 : 666	1 : 833	1 : 1	1 : 1.166
p_H	...	13.14	12.93	12.90	12.85	12.77	12.51	12.07	12.29

TABLE IV.

Aluminium sulphate and potassium tartrate.

K-tartrate = 1.695 g./100 c.c.

Al ₂ O ₃ .	K-tart. : Al ₂ O ₃	α_D^{15} .	$[\alpha]_D^{15}$.
0.0000 g /100 c.c.	1 : 0.000	0.9°	25.54°
0.1274	1 : 0.166	1.0	27.47
0.2548	1 : 0.333	1.2	30.76
0.3821	1 : 0.500	1.4	33.65
0.5095	1 : 0.666	1.5	34.09
0.6369	1 : 0.833	1.5	32.19
0.7642	1 : 1.000	1.5	30.48

TABLE V.

Aluminium sulphate and sodium tartrate.

Na-tartrate = 2.91 g./100 c.c.

Al ₂ O ₃ .	Na-tart. : Al ₂ O ₃ .	α_D^{15} .	$[\alpha]_D^{15}$.
0.0000 g./100 c.c.	1 : 0.000	1.8°	30.92°
0.2548	1 : 0.166	1.9	30.06
0.5095	1 : 0.333	2.0	29.24
0.7642	1 : 0.500	2.1	28.60
1.0190	1 : 0.666	2.3	29.26
1.2738	1 : 0.833	2.3	27.50
1.5285	1 : 1.000	2.3	25.20

Table V gives the results obtained with the polarimeter. It has been observed that *p* value results and the polarimeter investigations indicate the formation of complexes.

CONCLUSION.

Oxides of manganese and aluminium form complex with potassium tartrate in the ratio of 1:1 and 2:3 respectively. According to the view held by Dermois (*Bull. Soc. chim. Belg.*, 1927, 36, 64) the compounds will be of the type,

SUMMARY.

1. The complex formation between potassium tartrate and manganese chloride was studied in alkaline medium by means of polarimeter and potentiometer and it was found that a complex formation thus takes place when the molar proportions of potassium tartrate and manganese chloride is 1:1.

2. The formation of complex between alkali tartrate and aluminium sulphate in alkaline medium was also studied. The complex formation in this case is with two molecules of aluminium sulphate and three molecules of tartrate as found out by Yeu-ki-Heng (*Compt. rend.*, 1933, 196,259).

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